

Existence of solutions for Caputo fractional q -differential equations

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Abstract: In this work, we study existence and uniqueness of solutions for multi-point boundary value problem of nonlinear fractional differential equations with two fractional derivatives. By using the variety of fixed point theorems, such as Banach’s fixed point theorem, Leray-Schauder’s nonlinear alternative and Leray-Schauder’s degree theory, the existence of solutions is obtained. At the end, some illustrative examples are discussed.

Key words: q -Caputo’s integral, Caputo’s fractional derivative, fractional differential equations, Existence, Fixed point theorem, Leray-Schauders alternative.

1. Introduction

In this work, we discuss the existence and uniqueness of the solutions for multi-point boundary value problem of nonlinear fractional differential equations with two Caputo’s fractional orders

$$\begin{cases} {}^c D_q^\alpha x(t) = f(t, x(t)) + A J_q^\beta g(t, x(t)), & 0 < q < 1, t \in [0, T], \\ x(0) = J_q^{2-\alpha} x(0), x(T) = B J_q^{\alpha-1} x(T), \end{cases} \tag{1}$$

where D^α is the fractional q -derivative of the Caputo type of orders $\alpha \in]1, 2]$, J_q^ϑ is the Caputo’s fractional integral of order $\vartheta > 0, \vartheta \in \{\beta, 2 - \alpha, \alpha - 1\}$, A, B are real constants and $f, g : [0, T] \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, are continuous functions on $[0, T]$. The existence results for the multi-point boundary value problem (1) are based on variety of fixed point theorems, such as Banach’s fixed point theorem, Leray-Schauder’s non-linear alternative and Leray-Schauder’s degree theory. In recent years, boundary value problems of fractional q -differential equations involving a variety of boundary conditions have been investigated by several researchers, see for example [4, 12, 17, 18, 20]. By using fixed point theory, many researchers have established existence results for some q -differential equations. For more details, we refer the reader to [17, 19, 23, 25, 26] and the references therein. Fractional differential equations have recently been studied by several researchers. For some earlier work on the topic, we refer to [6, 8–11, 15], whereas some recent work on the existence theory of fractional hybrid differential equations can be found in [13, 14, 16, 22, 24]. Recently, many researchers have studied the existence of solutions for some fractional (q -fractional) difference equations. For some recent work on fractional differential equations, we refer to [4, 20, 23, 26] and the references therein.

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The rest of this paper is organized as follows: In section 2, basic definitions and notations are given. Section 3 is devoted to establish an existence and uniqueness result for the q -fractional problem (1). The first main result is based on Leray Schauder alternative and the second on Banach contraction principle. In section 4, an illustrative examples are discussed. .

1.1. Basic definitions

In this section, we present notation and some preliminary lemmas that will be used in the proofs of the main results.

For a real parameter $q \in \mathbb{R}^+ \setminus \{1\}$, a q -real number denoted by $[a]_q$ is defined by

$$[a]_q = \frac{1 - q^a}{1 - q}, \quad a \in \mathbb{R}.$$

The q -analogue of the Pochhammer symbol (q -shifted factorial) is defened as

$$(a; q)_0 = 1; (a; q)_k = \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} (1 - aq^i); \quad k \in \mathbb{N} \cap \{\infty\}.$$

The q -analogue of the exponent $(x - y)^k$ is

$$(x - y)_0 = 1; (x - y)_k = \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} (x - yq^i); \quad k \in \mathbb{N}; \quad x, y \in \mathbb{R}.$$

The q -gamma function $\Gamma_q(y)$ is defened as

$$\Gamma_q(y) = \frac{(1 - q)^{y-1}}{(1 - q)^{y-1}},$$

where $y \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0, -1, -2, \dots\}$. Observe that $\Gamma_q(y + 1) = [y]_q \Gamma_q(y)$.

Definition 1.1. [2] Let f be a function defined on $[0, 1]$. The fractional q -integral of the Riemann-Liouville type of orde $\alpha \geq 0$ is $(J_q^\alpha f)(t) = f(t)$ and

$$J_q^\alpha f(t) = \int_0^t \frac{(t - qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} f(s) d_qs = t^\alpha (1 - q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} f(tq^k); \quad \alpha > 0, t \in [0, 1].$$

Observe that $\alpha = 1$ in the Definition 1.1 yields the q -integral

$$J_q f(t) = \int_0^t f(s) d_qs = t(1 - q) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k f(tq^k).$$

For more details on q -integral and fractional q -integral, see Section 1.3 and Section 4.2 respectively in [1].

Remark 1.1. The q -fractional integration possesses the semigroup property (Proposition 4.3 [1])

$$J_q^\beta J_q^\alpha f = J_q^{\beta+\alpha} f; \quad \beta, \alpha \in \mathbb{R}^+,$$

Further, it has been shown in Lemma 6 of [3] that

$$J_q^\alpha(x)^{(\vartheta)} = \frac{\Gamma_q(\vartheta + 1)}{\Gamma_q(\vartheta + \alpha + 1)}(x)^{(\vartheta+\alpha)}; \quad 0 < x < a, \quad \alpha \in \mathbb{R}^+, \quad \vartheta \in (-1, \infty).$$

Before giving the definition of fractional q-derivative, we recall the concept of qderivative. We know that the q-derivative of a function $f(t)$ is defined as

$$(D_q f)(t) = \frac{f(t) - f(qt)}{t - qt}, \quad t \neq 0; \quad (D_q f)(0) = \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} (D_q f)(t).$$

Furthermore,

$$(D_q^0 f)(t) = f(t); \quad (D_q^n f)(t) = D_q(D_q^{n-1} f)(t); \quad n = 1, 2, 3 \dots \tag{2}$$

Definition 1.2. [1] The Caputo fractional q-derivative of order $\alpha > 0$ is defined by

$$(D_q^\alpha f)(t) = J_q^{[\alpha]-\alpha} D_q^{[\alpha]} f(t),$$

where $[\alpha]$ is the smallest integer greater than or equal to α .

Next we recall some properties involving Riemann-Liouville q-fractional integral and Caputo fractional q-derivative (Theorem 5.2 [1]).

$$J_q^\alpha D_q^\alpha f(t) = f(t) - \sum_{k=0}^{[\alpha]-1} \frac{t^k}{\Gamma_q(k+1)} (D_q^k f)(0^+), \quad \forall t \in]0, a], \quad \alpha > 0, \tag{3}$$

$${}^C D_q^\alpha J_q^\alpha f(t) = f(t), \quad \forall t \in]0, a], \quad \alpha > 0, . \tag{4}$$

To define the solution for problem (1), we need the following lemma.

Lemma 1.1. Let $h \in C([0, T], \mathbb{R})$ be a given function. Then the unique solution of the boundary value problem

$$\begin{cases} {}^C D_q^\alpha x(t) = h(t), \quad 0 < q < 1, t \in [0, T], \\ x(0) = J_q^{2-\alpha} x(0), x(T) = B J_q^{\alpha-1} x(T), \end{cases} \tag{5}$$

is given by

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) = & \int_0^t \frac{(t-qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} h(s) d_qs + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)t}{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)T-E} \left(\frac{B}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha-1)} \right. \\ & \left. \int_0^T (T-qs)^{(2\alpha-2)} h(s) d_qs - \int_0^T \frac{(T-qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} h(s) d_qs \right) \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where $E = BT^\alpha$ and $\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)T \neq E$.

Proof. Applying the operator J_q^α on both sides of fractional q-difference equation in (5), we get

$$x(t) = \int_0^t \frac{(t-qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} h(s) d_qs + c_0 + c_1 t, \tag{7}$$

for some constants $c_0; c_1 \in \mathbb{R}$. Since $J_q^{2-\alpha} x(0) = x(0)$, we have $c_0 = 0$. and

$$x(t) = BJ_q^{2\alpha-1}h(t) + c_1 \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)}.$$

from $x(T) = BJ_q^{\alpha-1}x(T)$, we have

$$c_1 = \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)}{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)T - E} \left(\frac{B}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha-1)} \int_0^T (T-qs)^{(2\alpha-2)}h(s)d_qs - \int_0^T \frac{(T-qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)}h(s)d_qs \right)$$

here $E = BT^\alpha$ and $\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)T \neq E$, so

$$x(t) = \int_0^t \frac{(t-qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)}h(s)d_qs + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)t}{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)T - E} \left(\frac{B}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha-1)} \int_0^T (T-qs)^{(2\alpha-2)}h(s)d_qs - \int_0^T \frac{(T-qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)}h(s)d_qs \right) \tag{8}$$

The proof is complete. □

2. Main Results

We denote by $X = C([0, T], \mathbb{R})$ the Banach space of all continuous functions from $[0, T]$ to \mathbb{R} endowed with a topology of uniform convergence with the norm defined by $\|x\| = \sup_{t \in [0, T]} |x(t)|$.

In view of Lemma 1.1, we define an operator $\hbar : X \rightarrow X$ by:

$$\begin{aligned} \hbar x(t) := & \int_0^t \frac{(t-qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)}f(s, x(s))d_qs + A \int_0^t \frac{(t-qs)^{(\beta+\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\beta+\alpha)}g(s, x(s))d_qs \\ & + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)t}{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)T - E} \left(\frac{B}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha-1)} \int_0^T (T-qs)^{(2\alpha-2)}f(s, x(s))d_qs \right. \\ & + \frac{BA}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha+\beta-1)} \int_0^T (T-qs)^{(2\alpha+\beta-2)}g(s, x(s))d_qs \\ & - \int_0^T \frac{(T-qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)}f(s, x(s))d_qs \\ & \left. - \frac{A}{\Gamma_q(\alpha+\beta)} \int_0^T (T-qs)^{(\alpha+\beta-1)}g(s, x(s))d_qs \right) \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Observe that the existence of a fixed point for the operator T implies the existence of a solution for the multi-point boundary value problem (1).

For convenience we introduce the notations:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Upsilon &= T^\alpha(1-q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} + |A|T^{\beta+\alpha}(1-q)^{\beta+\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{\beta+\alpha}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \\
&+ \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)T}{|[\alpha+1]_q T - E|} \left(|B|T^{2\alpha-1}(1-q)^{2\alpha-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha-1}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right. \\
&+ |B| |A|T^{2\alpha+\beta-1}(1-q)^{2\alpha+\beta-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha+\beta-1}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \\
&\left. + T^\alpha(1-q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} + |A|T^{\alpha+\beta}(1-q)^{\alpha+\beta} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{\alpha+\beta}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

In the following, we prove existence as well as existence and uniqueness results for multi-point boundary value problem (1) by applying a variety of fixed point theorems. Now, we present the existence and uniqueness of solutions of multi-point boundary value problem (1) by using Banach's fixed point theorem.

Theorem 2.1. *Let $f, g : [0, T] \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, be continuous functions satisfying the hypothesis (H_1) there exist nonnegative constants v_1, v_2 , such that for all $t \in [0, T]$ and all $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$, we have*

$$|f(t, x) - f(t, y)| \leq v_1 |x - y|, \quad |g(t, x) - g(t, y)| \leq v_2 |x - y|.$$

Then the multi-point boundary value problem (1) has a unique solution provided by $v\Upsilon < 1$, where $v = \max\{v_i : i = 1, 2\}$, Υ given by (10).

Proof. Let us define $L = \max\{L_i : i = 1, 2\}$, where L_i are finite numbers given by $L_1 = \sup_{t \in [0, T]} |f(t, 0)|$, $L_2 = \sup_{t \in [0, T]} |g(t, 0)|$. Setting $r \geq (vr + L)\Upsilon$, we show that $hB_r \subset B_r$, where $B_r = \{x \in X : \|x\| \leq r\}$.

For $x \in B_r$ and for each $t \in [0, T]$, from the definition of h and hypothesis (H_1) , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
&\|hx\| \\
&\leq \sup_{t \in [0, T]} \left\{ \int_0^t \frac{(t-qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} |f(s, x(s))| d_qs + |A| \int_0^t \frac{(t-qs)^{(\beta+\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\beta+\alpha)} |g(s, x(s))| d_qs \right. \\
&+ \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)t}{|[\alpha+1]_q T - E|} \left(\frac{|B|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha-1)} \int_0^T (T-qs)^{(2\alpha-2)} |f(s, x(s))| d_qs \right. \\
&+ |B| |A| \int_0^T \frac{(T-qs)^{(2\alpha+\beta-2)}}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha+\beta-1)} |g(s, x(s))| d_qs + \int_0^T \frac{(T-qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} |f(s, x(s))| d_qs \\
&\left. \left. + \frac{|A|}{\Gamma_q(\alpha+\beta)} \int_0^T (T-qs)^{(\alpha+\beta-1)} |g(s, x(s))| d_qs \right) \right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\leq \sup_{t \in [0, T]} \left\{ \int_0^t \frac{(t - qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} (|f(s, x(s)) - f(s, 0)| + |f(s, 0)|) d_qs \right. \\
 &\quad + |A| \int_0^t \frac{(t - qs)^{(\beta+\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\beta + \alpha)} (|g(s, x(s)) - g(s, 0)| + |g(s, 0)|) d_qs \\
 &\quad + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha + 1)t}{|[\alpha + 1]_q T - E|} \left(|B| \int_0^T \frac{(T - qs)^{(2\alpha-2)}}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha - 1)} (|f(s, x(s)) - f(s, 0)| + |f(s, 0)|) d_qs \right. \\
 &\quad + \frac{|B| |A|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha + \beta - 1)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(2\alpha+\beta-2)} (|g(s, x(s)) - g(s, 0)| + |g(s, 0)|) d_qs \\
 &\quad + \int_0^T \frac{(T - qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} (|f(s, x(s)) - f(s, 0)| + |f(s, 0)|) d_qs \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{|A|}{\Gamma_q(\alpha + \beta)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(\alpha+\beta-1)} (|g(s, x(s)) - g(s, 0)| + |g(s, 0)|) d_qs \right) \Big\} \\
 &\leq (vr + L) \sup_{t \in [0, T]} \left\{ \int_0^t \frac{(t - qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} d_qs + |A| \int_0^t \frac{(t - qs)^{(\beta+\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\beta + \alpha)} d_qs \right. \\
 &\quad + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha + 1)t}{|[\alpha + 1]_q T - E|} \left(\frac{|B|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha - 1)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(2\alpha-2)} d_qs \right. \\
 &\quad + \frac{|B| |A|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha + \beta - 1)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(2\alpha+\beta-2)} d_qs - \int_0^T \frac{(T - qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} d_qs \\
 &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{|A|}{\Gamma_q(\alpha + \beta)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(\alpha+\beta-1)} d_qs \right) \right\} \\
 &\leq (vr + L)\Upsilon \leq r,
 \end{aligned}$$

which implies that $\hbar B_r \subset B_r$. Now for $x, y \in B_r$ and for any $t \in [0, T]$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|\hbar x - \hbar y\| &\leq \sup_{t \in [0, T]} \left\{ \int_0^t \frac{(t - qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} |f(s, x(s)) - f(s, y(s))| d_qs \right. \\
 &\quad + |A| \int_0^t \frac{(t - qs)^{(\beta+\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\beta + \alpha)} |g(s, x(s)) - g(s, y(s))| d_qs \\
 &\quad + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha + 1)t}{|[\alpha + 1]_q T - E|} \left(|B| \int_0^T \frac{(T - qs)^{(2\alpha-2)}}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha - 1)} |f(s, x(s)) - f(s, y(s))| d_qs \right. \\
 &\quad + \frac{|B| |A|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha + \beta - 1)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(2\alpha+\beta-2)} |g(s, x(s)) - g(s, y(s))| d_qs \\
 &\quad + \int_0^T \frac{(T - qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} |f(s, x(s)) - f(s, y(s))| d_qs \\
 &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{|A|}{\Gamma_q(\alpha + \beta)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(\alpha+\beta-1)} |g(s, x(s)) - g(s, y(s))| d_qs \right) \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\leq \sup_{t \in [0, T]} \left\{ \int_0^t \frac{(t - qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} d_qs + |A| \int_0^t \frac{(t - qs)^{(\beta+\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\beta + \alpha)} d_qs \right. \\
 &\quad + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha + 1)t}{|[\alpha + 1]_q T - E|} \left(\frac{|B|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha - 1)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(2\alpha-2)} d_qs \right. \\
 &\quad + \frac{|B| |A|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha + \beta - 1)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(2\alpha+\beta-2)} d_qs - \int_0^T \frac{(T - qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha-)} d_qs \\
 &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{|A|}{\Gamma_q(\alpha + \beta)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(\alpha+\beta-1)} d_qs \right) \right\} v \|x - y\| \\
 &\leq \Upsilon v \|x - y\|
 \end{aligned}$$

which leads to $\|\hbar x - \hbar y\| \leq v \Upsilon \|x - y\|$. Since $v \Upsilon < 1$, \hbar is a contraction mapping. \square

Also, we give another variante of existence and uniqueness result based on the Hölder inequality.

Theorem 2.2. *Let $f, g : [0, T] \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, be continuous functions. In addition we assume that:*

(H₂) $|f(t, x) - f(t, y)| \leq u(t) |x - y|$, $|g(t, x) - g(t, y)| \leq k(t) |x - y|$, for each $t \in [0, T]$, $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$, where $u, k \in L^{\frac{1}{\delta}}([0, T], \mathbb{R}^+)$, $\delta \in (0, 1)$.

Denote $\|\theta\| = \left(\int_0^T |\theta(s)|^{\frac{1}{\delta}} d_qs \right)^{\delta}$, $\theta = u, k$.

If

$$\|u\| \Delta_1 + |A| \|k\| \Delta_2 < 1, \tag{11}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta_1 &= \frac{1}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^T (T - qs)^{\frac{(\alpha-1)}{1-\delta}} d_qs \right)^{1-\delta} \\
 &\quad + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha + 1)T}{|[\alpha + 1]_q T - E|} \left(\frac{|B|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha - 1)} \left(\int_0^T (T - qs)^{\frac{(2\alpha-2)}{1-\delta}} d_qs \right)^{1-\delta} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^T (T - qs)^{\frac{(\alpha-1)}{1-\delta}} d_qs \right)^{1-\delta} \right), \tag{12} \\
 \Delta_2 &= \frac{1}{\Gamma_q(\beta + \alpha)} \left(\int_0^T (t - qs)^{\frac{(\beta+\alpha-1)}{1-\delta}} d_qs \right)^{1-\delta} \\
 &\quad + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha + 1)T}{|[\alpha + 1]_q T - E|} \left(\frac{|B|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha + \beta - 1)} \left(\int_0^T (T - qs)^{\frac{(2\alpha+\beta-2)}{1-\delta}} d_qs \right)^{1-\delta} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{\Gamma_q(\alpha + \beta)} \left(\int_0^T (T - qs)^{\frac{(\alpha+\beta-1)}{1-\delta}} d_qs \right)^{1-\delta} \right),
 \end{aligned}$$

Then the multi-point boundary value problem (1) has a unique solution.

Proof. For $x, y \in X$ and $t \in [0, T]$, by Hölder inequality and using (H_2) , we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\hbar x - \hbar y| \\
 \leq & \sup_{t \in [0, T]} \left\{ \int_0^t \frac{(t - qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} u(s) |x(s) - y(s)| d_qs \right. \\
 & + |A| \int_0^t \frac{(t - qs)^{(\beta+\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\beta + \alpha)} k(s) |x(s) - y(s)| d_qs \\
 & + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha + 1)t}{|[\alpha + 1]_q T - E|} \left(\frac{|B|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha - 1)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(2\alpha-2)} u(s) |x(s) - y(s)| d_qs \right. \\
 & + \frac{|B||A|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha + \beta - 1)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(2\alpha+\beta-2)} k(s) |x(s) - y(s)| d_qs \\
 & + \int_0^T \frac{(T - qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} u(s) |x(s) - y(s)| d_qs \\
 & \left. + \frac{|A|}{\Gamma_q(\alpha + \beta)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(\alpha+\beta-1)} k(s) |x(s) - y(s)| d_qs \right\} \\
 \leq & \sup_{t \in [0, T]} \left\{ \frac{1}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^t (t - qs)^{\frac{(\alpha-1)}{1-\delta}} d_qs \right)^{1-\delta} \left(\int_0^t u(s)^{\frac{1}{\delta}} d_qs \right)^\delta \right. \\
 & + \frac{|A|}{\Gamma_q(\beta + \alpha)} \left(\int_0^t (t - qs)^{\frac{(\beta+\alpha-1)}{1-\delta}} d_qs \right)^{1-\delta} \left(\int_0^t k(s)^{\frac{1}{\delta}} d_qs \right)^\delta \\
 & + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha + 1)t}{|[\alpha + 1]_q T - E|} \left(\frac{|B|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha - 1)} \left(\int_0^T (T - qs)^{\frac{(2\alpha-2)}{1-\delta}} d_qs \right)^{1-\delta} \left(\int_0^T u(s)^{\frac{1}{\delta}} d_qs \right)^\delta \right. \\
 & + \frac{|B||A|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha + \beta - 1)} \left(\int_0^T (T - qs)^{\frac{(2\alpha+\beta-2)}{1-\delta}} d_qs \right)^{1-\delta} \left(\int_0^T k(s)^{\frac{1}{\delta}} d_qs \right)^\delta \\
 & + \frac{1}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} \left(\int_0^T (T - qs)^{\frac{(\alpha-1)}{1-\delta}} d_qs \right)^{1-\delta} \left(\int_0^T u(s)^{\frac{1}{\delta}} d_qs \right)^\delta \\
 & \left. + \frac{|A|}{\Gamma_q(\alpha + \beta)} \left(\int_0^T (T - qs)^{\frac{(\alpha+\beta-1)}{1-\delta}} d_qs \right)^{1-\delta} \left(\int_0^T k(s)^{\frac{1}{\delta}} d_qs \right)^\delta \right\} \|x - y\| \\
 = & (\Delta_1 \|u\| + |A| \Delta_2 \|k\|) \|x - y\|,
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\|\hbar x - \hbar y\| \leq (\Delta_1 \|u\| + |A| \Delta_2 \|k\|) \|x - y\|.$$

By the condition (11), it follows that \hbar is a contraction mapping. Hence, by the Banach's fixed point theorem \hbar has a unique fixed point which is the unique solution of the multi-point boundary value problem (1). Then, the proof is complete. \square

Now, we prove the existence of solutions of multi-point boundary value problem (1) by applying Leray-

Schauder nonlinear alternative [27].

Theorem 2.3. (Nonlinear alternative for single valued maps). Let X be a Banach space, C a closed, convex subset of X , Ω an open subset of C and $0 \in \Omega$. Suppose that $\hbar : \overline{\Omega} \rightarrow C$ is a continuous, compact (that is, $\hbar(\overline{\Omega})$ is a relatively compact subset of C) map. Then, either

- (i) \hbar has a fixed point in $\overline{\Omega}$, or,
- (ii) there is a $x \in \partial\Omega$ (the boundary of Ω in C) and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ with $x = \lambda\hbar x$.

Theorem 2.4. Assume that $f, g : [0, T] \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, are continuous functions. Suppose that:

(H₃) there exist nondecreasing functions $\psi, \psi_1 : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, and functions $b, b_1 \in L^1([0, T], \mathbb{R}^+)$, such that

$$|f(t, x)| \leq b(t)\psi(\|x\|), \quad |g(t, x)| \leq b_1(t)\psi_1(\|x\|), \quad \text{for all } (t, x) \in [0, T] \times \mathbb{R};$$

(H₄) there exists a constant $N > 0$ such that

$$\frac{N}{\|b\|_{L^1} \psi(N) \mathfrak{C}_1 + |A| \|b_1\|_{L^1} \psi_1(N) \mathfrak{C}_2} > 1,$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{C}_1 &= T^\alpha (1-q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \\ &\quad + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)T}{|[\alpha+1]_q T - E|} \left(|B| T^{2\alpha-1} (1-q)^{2\alpha-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha-1}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right) \\ &\quad + T^\alpha (1-q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_k}{(q; q)_k}, \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{C}_2 &= T^{\beta+\alpha} (1-q)^{\beta+\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{\beta+\alpha}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \\ &\quad + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)T}{|[\alpha+1]_q T - E|} \left(|B| T^{2\alpha+\beta-1} (1-q)^{2\alpha+\beta-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha+\beta-1}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right) \\ &\quad + T^{\alpha+\beta} (1-q)^{\alpha+\beta} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{\alpha+\beta}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k}, \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Then the multi-point boundary value problem (1) has at least one solution on $[0, T]$.

Proof. Let the operator $\hbar : X \rightarrow X$ be defined by (9). Firstly, we will show that \hbar maps bounded sets into bounded sets in X . For a number $r > 0$, let $B_r = \{x \in X : \|x\| \leq r\}$ be a bounded set in X . Then, for

$t \in [0, T]$ and (H_3) , we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\hbar x(t)| \\
 \leq & \int_0^t \frac{(t-qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} b(s) \psi(\|x\|) d_qs + |A| \int_0^t \frac{(t-qs)^{(\beta+\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\beta+\alpha)} b_1(s) \psi_1(\|x\|) d_qs \\
 & + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)t}{|[\alpha+1]_q T - E|} \left(\frac{|B|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha-1)} \int_0^T (T-qs)^{(2\alpha-2)} b(s) \psi(\|x\|) d_qs \right. \\
 & + \frac{|B||A|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha+\beta-1)} \int_0^T (T-qs)^{(2\alpha+\beta-2)} b_1(s) \psi_1(\|x\|) d_qs \\
 & + \int_0^T \frac{(T-qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} b(s) \psi(\|x\|) d_qs \\
 & \left. + \frac{|A|}{\Gamma_q(\alpha+\beta)} \int_0^T (T-qs)^{(\alpha+\beta-1)} b_1(s) \psi_1(\|x\|) d_qs \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Consequently,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|Tx\| & \leq \|b\|_{L^1} \psi(r) \left(T^\alpha (1-q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right. \\
 & + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)T}{|[\alpha+1]_q T - E|} \left(|B| T^{2\alpha-1} (1-q)^{2\alpha-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha-1}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right) \\
 & + T^\alpha (1-q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \Big) \\
 & + |A| \|b_1\|_{L^1} \psi_1(r) \left(T^{\beta+\alpha} (1-q)^{\beta+\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{\beta+\alpha}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right. \\
 & + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)T}{|[\alpha+1]_q T - E|} \left(|B| T^{2\alpha+\beta-1} (1-q)^{2\alpha+\beta-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha+\beta-1}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right) \\
 & \left. + T^{\alpha+\beta} (1-q)^{\alpha+\beta} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{\alpha+\beta}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right) \\
 & = \|b\|_{L^1} \psi(r) \mathfrak{C}_1 + |A| \|b_1\|_{L^1} \psi_1(r) \mathfrak{C}_2 = \ell.
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\|\hbar x\| \leq \ell.$$

Thus, \hbar maps bounded sets into bounded sets in X .

Next, we show that \hbar maps bounded sets into equicontinuous sets of X . Let $t_1, t_2 \in [0, T]$ with $t_1 < t_2$

and $x \in B_r$. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\hbar x(t_2) - \hbar x(t_1)| \\
 \leq & \frac{1}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} \int_0^{t_1} ((t_2 - qs)^{\alpha-1} - (t_1 - qs)^{\alpha-1}) |f(s, x(s))| d_qs \\
 & + \frac{1}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (t_2 - qs)^{\alpha-1} |f(s, x(s))| d_qs \\
 & + \frac{|A|}{\Gamma_q(\beta + \alpha)} \int_0^{t_1} ((t_2 - qs)^{\beta+\alpha-1} - (t_1 - qs)^{\beta+\alpha-1}) |g(s, x(s))| d_qs \\
 & + \frac{|A|}{\Gamma_q(\beta + \alpha)} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (t_2 - qs)^{\beta+\alpha-1} |g(s, x(s))| d_qs \\
 & + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha + 1)(t_2 - t_1)}{|\alpha + 1|_q T - E} \left(\frac{|B|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha - 1)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(2\alpha-2)} |f(s, x(s))| d_qs \right. \\
 & + \frac{|B| |A|}{\Gamma_q(2\alpha + \beta - 1)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(2\alpha+\beta-2)} |g(s, x(s))| d_qs \\
 & + \int_0^T \frac{(T - qs)^{(\alpha-1)}}{\Gamma_q(\alpha)} |f(s, x(s))| d_qs \\
 & \left. + \frac{|A|}{\Gamma_q(\alpha + \beta)} \int_0^T (T - qs)^{(\alpha+\beta-1)} |g(s, x(s))| d_qs \right) \\
 \leq & \|b\|_{L^1} \psi(r) (t_2^\alpha - t_1^\alpha) (1 - q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \\
 & + |A| \|b_1\|_{L^1} \psi_1(r) (t_2^{\beta+\alpha} - t_1^{\beta+\alpha}) (1 - q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{\beta+\alpha}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \\
 & + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha + 1)(t_2 - t_1)}{|\alpha + 1|_q T - E} \left(\|b\|_{L^1} \psi(r) |B| T^{2\alpha-1} (1 - q)^{2\alpha-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha-1}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right. \\
 & + \|b_1\|_{L^1} \psi_i(r) |B| |A| T^{2\alpha+\beta-1} (1 - q)^{2\alpha+\beta-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha+\beta-1}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \\
 & + T^\alpha \|b\|_{L^1} \psi(r) (1 - q)^{2\alpha-2} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha-2}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \\
 & \left. + |A| T^{\alpha+\beta} \|b_1\|_{L^1} \psi_1(r) (1 - q)^{\alpha+\beta} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{\alpha+\beta}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Obviously, the right-hand side of the above inequality tends to zero independently of $x \in B_r$ as $t_2 - t_1 \rightarrow 0$. Therefore, $\hbar : X \rightarrow X$ is completely continuous by application of the Arzela-Ascoli theorem.

Now, we can conclude the result by using the Leray-Schauder's nonlinear alternative theorem. Consider the equation $x = \lambda \hbar x$ for $0 < \lambda < 1$ and assume that x be a solution. Then, using the computations in proving

that \hbar is bounded, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \|x\| = \|\lambda \hbar x\| \\
 & \leq \|b\|_{L^1} \psi(r) \left(T^\alpha (1-q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right. \\
 & \quad + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)T}{|[\alpha+1]_q T - E|} \left(|B| T^{2\alpha-1} (1-q)^{2\alpha-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha-1}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right) \\
 & \quad + T^\alpha (1-q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \Bigg) \\
 & \quad + |A| \|b_1\|_{L^1} \psi_1(r) \left(T^{\beta+\alpha} (1-q)^{\beta+\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{\beta+\alpha}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right. \\
 & \quad + \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)T}{|[\alpha+1]_q T - E|} \left(|B| T^{2\alpha+\beta-1} (1-q)^{2\alpha+\beta-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha+\beta-1}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right) \\
 & \quad \left. + T^{\alpha+\beta} (1-q)^{\alpha+\beta} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{\alpha+\beta}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\|x\|}{\|b\|_{L^1} \psi(r) \mathfrak{C}_1 + |A| \|b_1\|_{L^1} \psi_1(r) \mathfrak{C}_2} \leq 1.$$

By (H_4) , there exists N such that $N \neq \|x\|$. Let us set

$$\Omega =: \{x \in X : \|x\| < N\}.$$

We see that the operator $\hbar : \bar{\Omega} \rightarrow X$ is continuous and completely continuous. From the choice of Θ , there is no $x \in \partial\Omega$ such that $x = \lambda \hbar x$ for some $0 < \lambda < 1$. Consequently, by the nonlinear alternative of Leray-Schauder's type, we deduce that \hbar has a fixed point $x \in \bar{\Omega}$ which is a solution of the multi-point boundary value problem (1). This completes the proof. \square

3. Application

To illustrate our main results, we treat the following examples.

Example 3.1. *Let us consider the following multi-point boundary value problem*

$$\begin{cases} D_{0,5}^{\frac{3}{2}} x(t) = f(t, x(t)) + A J_{0,5}^\beta g(t, x(t)), & t \in [0, 1], \\ x(0) = J_{0,5}^{\frac{1}{2}} x(0), x(1) = B J_{0,5}^{\frac{1}{2}} x(1), \end{cases} \tag{15}$$

For this example, we have $\alpha = \frac{3}{2}, T = 1, q = \frac{1}{2}, A = 1, \beta = \frac{1}{3}, B = 2$, and $f(t, x) = \frac{x(t)}{16\pi(2te^{t^3+4} + t^2 \cos(t)+1)}$,

$g(t, x) = \frac{x(t)}{20\pi(e^t(15+\pi)+7+e^{2t} \ln(t+1))}$. Also for $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$ and $t \in [0, 1]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 |f(t, x) - f(t, y)| & \leq \frac{1}{16\pi} |x - y|, \\
 |g(t, x) - g(t, y)| & \leq \frac{1}{20\pi} |x - y|,
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
 v_1 &= \frac{1}{16\pi}, v_2 = \frac{1}{20\pi}, \\
 \Upsilon &= (1-q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} + (1-q)^{\beta+\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{\beta+\alpha}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \\
 &+ \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)}{|\lceil \alpha+1 \rceil_q - E|} \left(2(1-q)^{2\alpha-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha-1}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right. \\
 &+ 2(1-q)^{2\alpha+\beta-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha+\beta-1}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \\
 &\left. + (1-q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} + (1-q)^{\alpha+\beta} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{\alpha+\beta}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right),
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$v = \max \{v_i, i = 1, 2\}.$$

Therefore, we have

$$v\Upsilon < 1$$

Hence, all the hypotheses of Theorem 2.1 are satisfied. Thus, by the conclusion of Theorem 2.1, multi-point boundary value problem (15) has a unique solution.

Example 3.2. As a second illustrative example, let us take

$$\begin{cases} D_{0.5}^{\frac{4}{3}}x(t) = f(t, x(t)) + AI_{0.5}^\beta g_i(t, x(t)), & t \in [0, 1], \\ x(0) = J_{0.5}^{\frac{2}{3}}x(0), x(1) = BJ_{0.5}^{\frac{1}{3}}x(1), \end{cases} \tag{16}$$

Here, $\alpha = \frac{4}{3}$, $q = \frac{1}{2}$, $T = 1$, $A = \frac{1}{9}$, $\beta = \frac{1}{5}$, $B = \sqrt{2}$, and

$$f(t, x) = e^{t^2} \frac{|x|^3(t)}{(1+te^t)(3x^2+3t^{2e}+t \sin(t))}, \quad g(t, x) = \frac{x(t)}{6\pi+t^2} + \frac{(1+e^{t^2})}{2\pi+10 \sin(t)+3},$$

Then we can find that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathfrak{C}_1 &= (1-q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \\
 &+ \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)}{|\lceil \alpha+1 \rceil_q - E|} \left(\sqrt{2}(1-q)^{2\alpha-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha-1}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right) \\
 &+ (1-q)^\alpha \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^\alpha; q)_k}{(q; q)_k}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{C}_2 &= (1-q)^{\beta+\alpha} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{\beta_1+\alpha}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \\ &+ \frac{\Gamma_q(\alpha+1)}{|\alpha+1|_q - E} \left(\sqrt{2}(1-q)^{2\alpha+\beta-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{2\alpha+\beta_1-1}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \right) \\ &+ (1-q)^{\alpha+\beta} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q^k \frac{(q^{\alpha+\beta}; q)_k}{(q; q)_k} \end{aligned}$$

Clearly,

$$\begin{aligned} |f(t, x)| &= \left| e^{t^2} \frac{|x|^3(t)}{(1+te^t)(3x^2+3t^2e+t \sin(t))} \right| \leq \frac{e^{t^2}}{3(1+te^t)} (|x|), \\ |g(t, x)| &= \left| \frac{x(t)}{6\pi+t^2} + \frac{(1+e^{t^2})}{2\pi+10 \sin(t)+3} \right| \leq \frac{1+e^{t^2}}{12\pi} (2|x|+6), \end{aligned}$$

Choosing $b(t) = \frac{e^{t^2}}{3(1+te^t)}$, $b_1(t) = \frac{2(1+e^{t^2})}{12\pi}$, and $\psi(|x|) = |x|$, $\psi_1(|x|) = |x| + 3$, we can show that

$$\frac{N}{\|b\|(N)\mathfrak{C}_1 + |A| \|b_1\|(N+3)\mathfrak{C}_2} > 1,$$

which implies $N > 1$. Hence, by Theorem 2.4, the multi-point boundary value problem (16) has at least one solution on $[0, 1]$.

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